

JULY/AUGUST 1996
NO. 181

Piano

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Nancy Burkhalter apprenticed a master craftsman in Chicago in 1974 as a hedge against a wobbly economy. She's been tuning ever since. She now plies her trade in Laramie, Wyoming, and teaches in the English Department at the University of Colorado, Denver.

Jeanne Kierman Fischer is Artist Teacher of Piano at the Shepherd School of Music at Rice University. You can hear the Fischer Duo (*Imaginés: Music of French Masters*, NR 238-CD) and see them on a Discovery Channel documentary, "Time and Music," to be aired next season.

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PIANO & KEYBOARD

(ISSN 0031-9554) is published bimonthly in
January, March, May, July, September, and
November by SparrowHawk Press, 223 San
Anselmo Avenue #3, San Anselmo, CA
94960. Second-class postage paid at San
Anselmo, CA, and additional mailing offices.
Printed in USA.

POSTMASTER: Please send address changes
to PIANO & KEYBOARD, PO Box 2626, San
Anselmo, CA 94979-2626.

A single issue costs \$4.95; an individual
subscription is \$23.95 per year;
institutional subscriptions are \$36. per year.
Foreign subscribers must order air-mail
delivery. Add \$7.50 per year for Canada/Pan
Am; \$15. elsewhere, payable in local funds
drawn on U.S. bank. Please address all
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Telephone (415) 458-8672, Fax (415) 458-
2955. All contents © 1996 by SparrowHawk
Press, Inc., James Keough, Publisher.

The Composer as Collaborator

By Jeanne Kierman Fischer

The Fischer Duo, Norman and Jeanne Kierman Fischer, find enjoyment and challenge in playing new music with the composer's input.

“**S**taccatissimo! It's not dry enough! It's got to be more neurotic!” George Rochberg yells from the back of the hall as I attempt to find just the sound that he wants from the piano. “Let's try the *agitato* with much more energy and tons of *rubato*.” George is gesticulating wildly as he stomps up to the front of the stage toward Norman Fischer, cellist and my duo partner. I try one more time, thinking it will never be quite passionate, devastating, or “on the edge” enough for George. It is January 24, 1993, the night before the premiere of his new work, *Sonata Aria*.

Members of the Fischer family have assembled for this auspicious event, each

having contributed generously towards the commission of the piece, a memorial to Gerald Fischer, Norman's father. Gerald was a great supporter of the arts, and George felt a strong kinship with him during his long battle with cancer. The music reflects the anguish of this life struggle. It is a 29-minute song-like elegy, tonal and atonal, craggy, declamatory, risky (see Example 1).

Working with a composer as passionate and clear in his ideas as Rochberg makes us feel that he is sitting on stage with us. Though we are the only two performing, George is there, coaching us in every phrase. We are actually a trio, duo performers plus composer. As a pianist, I am fortunate to have an intense and

long-term duo partnership with Norman, and I see the collaboration with living composers as a logical extension of the collaborative spirit.

The Fischer Duo came into being in 1971, and we have gone through many phases in our working relationship. At first, much of our creative energies were used to get the mechanics of a performance to work. We relied on visual cues to help us through the thornier passages. More recently, we depend instead on listening to the shaping and phrasing of each of our lines. I can often tell by the way Norman opens up his bow speed where he feels the inevitable goal of a phrase, and what color, dynamic, and impulse he will use. It is a much more natural way to interact, yielding a more sophisticated result. Frequently, one of us will walk off-stage after a concert and say, “How did you know I was going to take that big timing? I didn't even know myself until it happened. You were right with me!”

In works we have played many times, it's sometimes hard to keep them fresh. Although Norman and I don't seem to tire of our “old friends,” we come up with different performance goals for different studies of each work. Sometimes it will be mood, as it was in a recent performance of the Beethoven *D-Major Sonata*, Op. 102, No. 2. The miraculous slow movement is a consummate artistic challenge to suspend the large spaces and to be vulnerable to Beethoven's inner intensity. We decided to “sculpt” the lines to truly reinforce the dark, tragic qualities of D-minor and, in the middle section, to open up the resonance so that it “glowed” with the hope of D-Major.

Sometimes structural issues dominate our thinking. We recently traversed the three Brahms sonatas, and in revisiting the fugal finale of the *E-minor Sonata*, decided to accentuate the metric counterpoint. In the subject, Brahms clearly wants the metric stress on the second beat, and later switches to the first beat in the countersubject. In rehearsal, we found that when we really committed to that type of articulation, it posed a whole new set of ensemble problems that we had never before experienced. But the tension and power of the music were also more than we had ever experienced. Each new performance goal is only possible with years of experience and adds a new level to our understanding of the work.

Used with the permission of Robert Sirata

Example 1: Measures 53-58 of George Rochberg's Sonata Aria, which was commissioned as a memorial to Norman's father Gerald Fischer.

I am frequently asked, "What is it like to have a professional partnership with your husband?" Many other musician couples have been amazed that we could possibly work together onstage. We feel it's the most natural extension of our personal relationship. At the beginning, of course, things were not so easy. Rehearsals were about learning to communicate effectively and not letting easily bruised egos get the better of us. Later we learned to create a balance between critical comments and affirmation. Those communication skills helped us outside of the musical arena as well. Like a marriage, it just takes time to build an ensemble, with the intent that the music will be helped, instead of limited, by the personalities.

Pianists who enjoy ensemble playing are most often gregarious by nature. It seems that collaborative pianists have certain personality traits in common—a genuine pleasure in negotiating an interpretation amid the tussles of rehearsal, a love of getting to know others, and a conviction that the whole is greater than the sum of its parts. The most obvious personality trait is empathy, the ability to get "inside the skin" of another.

Sometimes such empathy can create problems. On one occasion I was asked to play a recital with a visiting string player. It was a difficult program techni-

cally: a Bach sonata I had not played in years, a Hindemith sonata I had coached but had never played, and a complex contemporary work. We rehearsed for several days, a couple of hours each session. By the evening of the recital, I so empathized with his tense way of playing that every muscle in my arms was in knots. Exhausted, I wondered whether I could even play. Afterwards, on the advice of a friend, I took a complete body massage. By the next day, I was ready to play the complete Beethoven cello sonatas (in one evening) with no pain. It was a recovery made all the more speedy by the fact that I was once again collaborating with Norman, a most natural and relaxed performer.

With the exception of performing in a collaborative situation myself, nothing gives me more pleasure than introducing talented young pianists to the skills involved in playing with their own student colleagues—other pianists, singers, and instrumentalists. Although young instrumentalists and singers can acquire ensemble experience early on, pianists more often have to wait until their pianism is at quite a high level in order to negotiate the complexities of chamber music. For the pianist, ensemble playing demands acute listening, subtle pedaling, finely tuned dynamic control, totally dependable rhythm, and a wonderfully

colorful imagination for sound—all huge learning challenges for the young pianist.

Sometimes, when pianists experience misfortunes, we are fond of blaming the eccentricities of a particular piano. I like to tell the story of the first time that I played the Brahms *C-minor Piano Quartet*, Op. 60, an extraordinarily demanding and dark piece. I had been playing for a number of years with the same professional ensemble in the New England region, and we waded through many large works before we felt we were ready for this particular work. After a rather lengthy period of rehearsals battling out such issues as balance, phrasing, and large conception, we felt we were really prepared for our first performance at a splendid large church in Burlington, Vermont. As was our custom, we drove to the concert with plenty of time for me to try out the piano and check the acoustics of the hall. To our dismay, the custodian told us the heating system was malfunctioning. The director of the chamber music series informed us that the concert was to be performed in the adjacent parish hall on a dilapidated upright instead of the expected seven-foot grand. However, in spite of (or perhaps because of) all the adversity, the performance was even more emotional and heartfelt, a true collaborative triumph of each of our four human spirits rising above the limitations of a mechanical instrument.

Several of my own mentors displayed exuberance for collaborative performance. My mother, a wonderful pianist and organist, had a steady stream of musicians through our house in various places of the world. When I was 12, we lived in Nairobi, Kenya, and I recall a visit by my mother's friend, Lamar Crowson, then pianist with London's Melos Ensemble. He had come from England to play concerts, but also to hear examinations for the Royal Schools of Music. After enjoying a sumptuous feast, he discovered that I was participating in the examinations and a subsequent competition. At his request, I obediently performed for him, not expecting the extravagant coaching that ensued. Not only did I win the competition, but the experience also changed forever my own personal artistic expectations. Ever since, I have been inspired by Crowson's career, which has not only included solo recordings of Clementi and Haydn, but also

long-term musical collaborations with Pierre Fournier and Jacqueline Du Pré.

In addition to Crowson, it has been a great privilege for me to have had close contact with other fabulous pianists who are also superb collaborators. I have learned from Gilbert Kalish's rhythmic incisiveness and energy, as well as from his passionate personal integrity. From Menahem Pressler, I learned how to be compellingly clear about both dynamic shaping and exaggerated character. These days, I'm delighted that piano students around the country have more role models who garner respect both for solo, as well as collaborative, artistry.

The desire to be in on the birth of a work seems the very highest form of musical collaboration. In college I had a taste of one of my theory teacher's new scores, and my appetite for new music, whether that meant works by living artists or unknown works by past composers, was whetted. When my husband's Concord String Quartet was formed, it was clear from the beginning that they were passionate about new and unknown music. Quartet scores often arrived in the mail, and there was general excitement about hearing the ones voted to be worked into the repertoire. In the first year, rehearsals were held in our back room. I'll always remember the ear-stretching juxtaposition of my own private practicing of a late Beethoven sonata and the ConCORDS working out a lengthy quartet in a 24-note row of evenly tempered quarter-tones!

In tandem with the quartet's discovery of new works, the Fischer Duo searched for new and forgotten works for cello and piano. In Aaron Cohen's *Encyclopedia of Women Composers*, we stumbled across three pieces by Nadia Boulanger. We applied at the interlibrary loan desk at Dartmouth College, and there was an eight-month hunt to find the pieces, all published separately. The first was found rather quickly at the Kansas State Teachers' College at Emporia. The third was found months later, fallen behind the stacks in the Harvard library. Even later, the second piece (two fragile pages of music) arrived, at the cost of \$12, directly from Heugel in Paris. These compositional gems have become a mainstay of our repertoire.

Relationships with living composers have been at the center of our passion in

music and are reflected in our concerts. (Recently, a loyal Houston concertgoer asked about our upcoming program of Brahms sonatas, "Do you expect an appearance by the composer?") Our oldest association has been with Robert Sirota, an undergraduate classmate of ours who is now Director of the Peabody School of Music. Norman and Bob settled on their first commission at adjacent shaving sinks in the freshman dormitory at Oberlin, and Bob has written a number of pieces for us since then. The *Sonata* (1988) is one of the most significant. Premiered at the American Music Festival at the National Gallery of Art in Washington D.C., the piece was in com-

memoration of Bob's father, who had recently died from cancer. The work resonated with us personally because, although we were playing it for Bob's father, we felt as if we were playing it for Norman's father who passed away that same year. Although profound and dark, the piece also breathes moments of levity and spiritual brightness. Bob knows us so well that he has written into the music not only our personalities, but the egalitarian nature of our duo—passionate surging of the accompanimental lines against the tortured and haunting opening melody. (see Figure 2)

A longtime friend of the Concord Quartet, David Stock, now composer-in-

The image shows a handwritten musical score for a piece titled "Sonata" by Robert Sirota, dated 1987-1988. The score is written on ten systems of staves. The top system is for the Cello (C) and the second system is for the Piano (P). The tempo is marked "Allegro moderato a appassionato" and the time signature is 4/4. The score includes various musical notations such as notes, rests, dynamics (f, mf, mp, dim), and articulation marks. There are also some handwritten annotations and a circled number 10. At the bottom of the page, there is a copyright notice: "© 1989 Robert Sirota ASCAP".

Example 2: Robert Sirota's *Sonata* was written for the Fischer Duo in memory of Sirota's father.

residence at Duquesne and conductor of the Pittsburgh New Music Ensemble, provided another interesting notion of “partnership” in music. Out of that friendship and Norman’s previous appearances on the wonderful Market Square Concert Series, came the idea of playing a recital of music by composers from Harrisburg, Pennsylvania. A three-fold partnership was hatched. The first partnership was joint funding by Lucy Miller, director of Market Square Concerts and the Pennsylvania Arts Council; the second was between the composer and the Fischer

music we have championed for many years. We began working on his marvelous *Capriccio* (1985) at Tanglewood in 1989, on the recommendation of Yo-Yo Ma. At the time, Bolcom was in the area with his wife and singer, Joan Morris, doing a program at a local concert series. We shared a meal and old times, and Bill asked to hear the *Capriccio*, a work in four movements that concludes with a fabulous tango (in homage to Ernesto Nazareth, 1863-1934). After we played through it, Bill said he loved our performance. We asked him about

had changed for us collaborative pianists. Elliott and Helen Carter had come to the recital, and I overheard Helen say, “Now why do pianists these days need to have their piano sticks up all the way? The cello looks so tiny next to that nine-foot monster!”

Being part of a musical community can also breed wonderful opportunities to collaborate with composer colleagues. I feel fortunate to be among the fine composers at the Shepherd School of Music at Rice University. It has been an extraordinary pleasure to play Ellsworth Milburn’s effective *Character Pieces* (1985), five movements in arch form with large-scale, dramatic “Fantasies” in the outer movements, an “Intermezzo” in the center (inspired by Brahms Op. 118 #2) and “Nocturnes” in movements 2 and 4. The second nocturne is a hauntingly ethereal version of “Amazing Grace” (harmonics in the cello) with dulcimer-like strumming inside the piano. Paul Cooper’s *Elegies* (1991) is a lyrical memorial to his wife and several close friends. Richard Lavenda’s *Memory’s Motion* (1990) is an energetic and nostalgic work inspired by the composer’s remembrance of studying cello with Norman as an undergraduate at Dartmouth and rejoicing in our new relationship as colleagues. Next year, we are looking forward to playing a new work by Samuel Jones commemorating our 25th anniversary season.

In this celebratory season, we are being given the wonderful opportunity of sharing our musical partnership as Artistic Ambassadors for the United States Information Agency. The collaborations will be two-fold. First, as the Fischer Duo, we will collaborate in presenting lecture-recitals on American composers such as Bolcom, Milburn, Carter, and others, and master classes and concerts of American works as well as standard repertoire to the people of South America. Second, the American embassies will collaborate with concert presenters, universities, and conservatories in Argentina, Chile, Paraguay, and Bolivia to set up our residency activities. It also gives us another opportunity to look for music not ordinarily heard in our North American concert halls. We are currently looking at dozens of scores by composers from these countries. Tangos, anyone? †

Jim Caldwell

Jeanne and Norman have moved beyond visual clues to a more intuitive understanding of their collaboration on difficult passages.

Duo; the third was between David and his wife of 25 years, as the commission was a musical anniversary present! The other works on the program were by Rochberg (the beautiful *Ricordanza*), Vincent Persichetti, and Samuel Barber. The Stock piece, *Partners* (1988), is a very expressive, compelling work. The middle movement is a scherzo with cello pizzicato and staccato piano so interconnected and cleverly conceived that the listener finds it difficult to distinguish between the two instruments. The concert itself was a joyous recognition of the musical wealth of Pennsylvania, and provided all of us a unique opportunity for different sorts of collaborations.

William Bolcom, a superb collaborative pianist, is another composer whose

Nazareth, and Bill proceeded to play, by heart, several delicious gems of tango poetry full of complex counterpoint and bawdy humor. (What an extravagant and prolific musical memory this man has!)

In 1993, at New York’s Merkin Hall, we played an all-American music concert to celebrate important birthdays of Bolcom, George Rochberg, and Elliott Carter. In addition to these composer’s works, we also presented the New York premiere of a stunning opus by the brilliant young composer, Augusta Read Thomas (now teaching at the Eastman School). She had written *Chant* for us in 1991—a colorful, lyrical and internally dramatic duo. In the green room, after the concert, I chuckled over how times